

Study of Heavy Metal Accumulation in Common Carp (*Cyprinus Carpio L.*) Tissues as an Indicator of Sustainable Development in Aquatic Environments

Ban Salman Kadhim

Animal production, College of agriculture, University of summer, Iraq

Abeer Salim Ali

Animal production, College of agriculture, University of summer, Iraq

Adnan Jawad Ahmed

Veterinary public health, College of agriculture, University of summer, Iraq

Suggested Citation

Kadhim, B.S., Ali, A.S., & Ahmed, A.J. (2025). Study of Heavy Metal Accumulation in Common Carp (*Cyprinus Carpio L.*) Tissues as an Indicator of Sustainable Development in Aquatic Environments. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(1), 353-359.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(1\).31](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(1).31)

Abstract:

The study was conducted to determine the extent of heavy metal accumulation in aquatic organisms important for consumption and to assess the reflection of the aquatic environment in Wasit Governorate, Iraq. Samples were taken from three locations: the first from the river, the second from floating cages, and the third from earthen ponds, as these two systems are the most widespread for fish farming in Iraq.

The results showed that the gill tissues were the most affected by the environment due to their direct contact with the aquatic surroundings. It was observed that the accumulation rates of these elements in fish muscle tissues were the lowest compared to

liver and gill tissues. All concentrations were within the permissible limits for human consumption. The results can help predict the state of the aquatic environment in Iraq and work towards the sustainable development of water and animal resources.

Keywords: *sustainable development, Heavy metals, the Accumulation, Tissues, Common Carp (Cyprinus Carpio L.).*

Introduction

Fish culture is the fundamental unit for preserving fish resources ,producing fish and improving their quality in specialized breeding farms ,this is to provide animal protein for human consumption and to meet apportion of the increasing human demand for animal protein (abas et.al.,2016) the demand for fish meat increases every year ,and in order to maintain the level of individual consumption ,fish production needs to increase over the next twenty year by

approximately 40 million tons above the current production levels (FAO,2016).

The fish farming sector is one of the most environmentally safe sectors as it a low-pollution source compared to other animal production sectors (Nijda et. al., 2012). this has made it the fastest growing sector globally. due to the reduced productivity of natural water caused by pollution and over fishing, fishing farming through specialized breeding systems has

become one of the solutions to increase fish production (Kassam et.al., 2011).

Water plays a crucial role in fish production processes, and pollution of this water with heavy metals is a significant issue due to industrial and agricultural progress, which has a major impact as a result of dumping waste in rivers and lakes. The bioaccumulation of heavy metals in fish varies depending on the method of absorption, the type of metal, and the type of fish. The concentrations of these metals in the aquatic environment do not indicate the degree of pollution without their accumulation in aquatic organisms (Ibrahim et.al., 2020). Sources of pollution with heavy metals such as copper and zinc are the result of natural sources such as earthy rocks, mineral or industrial ores, household waste, or agricultural waste that affect the ecosystem, which in turn leads to their accumulation and difficulty of decomposition, even if they are in low concentrations (hassan et.al., 2010; Fahad ,2014). Heavy metals accumulate in fish at a higher rate than their proportions in water due to their feeding on algae and small organisms in addition to organic materials found in the aquatic environment (Olaifa et.al., 2004). Heavy metals enter either directly through food or indirectly through the gills (Blackkmore, 2000). The toxic effect is transmitted from one organism to another through feeding and increasing their concentration in living bodies. In metabolism, it sometimes leads to death when it exceeds the permissible limits. Heavy metals have the ability to integrate and move in food baskets until they reach humans who are located in the food pyramid (Rasheed, 2012).

This study was aimed to conducted to determine the amount of accumulation that occurs in fish raised within the farming systems and the aquatic environment and the extent of its impact on the consumer and the sustainability of production and possibility of using aquatic organisms as indicators of water quality and conducting sustainable development on these Aquatic systems.

Materials and Methods

Sample Collection

Samples were collected from rivers, cages, and earthen ponds, focusing on common carp (*Cyprinus carpio L.*).

Sample Preparation (APHA, 2003)

- Approximately 2-3 grams of gill and liver tissue and 5 grams of muscle tissue were weighed for each sample.
- The samples were placed in clean glass bottles, to which 10 mL of concentrated nitric acid was added.
- The samples were left for 48-72 hours at room temperature to complete the digestion process.
- The solution was then diluted with deionized water to a final volume of 25 mL and filtered using filter paper.
- Using an atomic absorption spectrometer, the heavy metals were quantified and expressed in micrograms.

Statistical Analysis

The data were analyzed using the SPSS statistical analysis program according to the Completely Randomized Design (CRD) ((SPSS,2020). The mathematical model for a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with two interacting factors is represented as follows:

$$Y_{ijk} = \mu + A_i + B_j + (AB)_{ij} + \epsilon_{ijk} \quad (1)$$

Where:

Y_{ijk} is the observed value.

μ is the overall mean.

A_i is the effect of the first factor ($i = 1, 2, \dots, a$).

B_j is the effect of the second factor ($j = 1, 2, \dots, b$).

$(AB)_{ij}$ is the interaction effect between the two factors.

ϵ_{ijk} is the random error associated with the observation Y_{ijk}

Results and Discussion

The results collected from the current study indicate that fish serve as a mirror reflecting the purity or pollution of their environment. They can be used as indicators to understand the aquatic environment and manage it properly to achieve sustainable development. According to the results obtained from samples collected from three locations where fish are found, two of

which are fish farming systems (cages and earthen ponds) that constitute the majority of fish farming systems in Iraq, and comparing these results with samples caught from the river, the study found a significant difference in the concentration of zinc and copper between samples taken from rivers, cages, and earthen ponds. Significant differences were also recorded between cages and both earthen ponds and the river in the concentrations of cadmium and mercury, whereas no significant differences were found between the river and earthen ponds as shown in the table below.

Table 1. Shown the Concentration Heavy Metals in Major of Fish Farming and River

Sample Source	Zn	Cu	Cd	Hg
River	105.31±12.27 b	43.49±4.35 a	13.89±1.76 a	0.101±0.0012 b
Cages	99.97±11.37 c	37.36±3.61 b	11.41±1.44 b	0.0018±0.003 a
Earthen Ponds	118.91±14.98 a	32.05±3.89 c	13.30±1.83 a	0.0083±0.0029 b

Note: * Columns containing different letters indicate significant differences between them $p \leq 0.05$

The results align with those of (Jasim and Fahad, 2023), who reported significant differences in the concentration of elements in fish raised in cages. They also align with (Balq et.al.,2023), regarding significant differences in fish caught from natural environments. Concerning earthen ponds, the results are consistent with Joudeh and kadhim (2023) which indicated significant differences among the studied samples.

The results indicated significant differences in the concentration of heavy metals (zinc, copper, cadmium, and mercury) in the studied tissues. It was observed that the lowest values were recorded in the muscle tissue compared to the gills and liver. This is because the gills are in constant direct contact with water, leading to higher accumulation of these metals, and similarly, the liver, being the primary organ that deals with these elements, shows higher accumulation. These findings align with AL-Khafaji and Lazim (2013) who recorded the

lowest levels of accumulation in muscle tissues. Muscle tissue is the main consumed part of fish and can be considered safe for consumers, provided these concentrations remain within safe limits for human consumption as shown in Figure 1.

There is a noticeable increase in the concentrations of heavy metals in the gill tissues of the fish compared to their concentrations in the muscle tissues. Zn showed a significant increase in the sample taken from earthen ponds compared to samples taken from cages and the river, while no significant differences were observed for the other elements among the samples as shown figure2. Previous studies have also shown significant differences in the accumulation of heavy metals among different tissues in the body, due to the activity level of each tissue and its method of dealing with and expelling waste from the body (Radeef et.al.,2013).

Figure 1. Illustrates the Concentration of Heavy Metals in the Gill, Liver, and Muscle Tissues of the Fish. Different Letters within the Same Element Indicate Significant Differences $p \leq 0.05$.

Figure 2. Illustrates the Concentration of Elements in the Gills of Fish from the River, Cages, and Earthen Ponds. Different Letters Indicating Element Concentration Signify Significant Differences

From the observed concentrations of element accumulation in the liver, it was found that the concentration of copper did not show significant differences among the three systems (figure 3). However, fish samples caught from the river exhibited significant differences compared to the other systems. Mercury showed a significant difference in the cage system compared to the

other systems. All recorded values were within permissible limits, The current study, along with previous research, indicates a consensus that heavy metal accumulation is higher in liver tissues compared to muscle tissues. This is because the liver directly handles the excretion of waste from the body (Farhood, 2015).

Figure3. Illustrates the Concentration of Elements in the Liver of Fish from the River, Cages, and Earthen Ponds. Different Letters Indicating Element Concentration Signify Significant Differences

The concentrations of the studied elements in the muscle tissues were the lowest compared to the liver and gill tissues (figure 4). There were no significant differences in the concentrations of cu, cd, and Hg. However, significant differences were noted in the Zn concentrations in muscle tissue from samples taken from earthen ponds compared to other systems, The accumulation

levels of elements in muscle tissues were the lowest compared to other tissues, which aligns with studies indicating lower accumulation in muscle tissues. Since muscle is the primary part consumed, this makes it safe for human consumption (Khanipour et. al.,2018; Othman et.al., 2023).

Figure4. Illustrates the Concentration of Elements in the Meet of Dish from the River, Cages, and Earthen Ponds. Different Letters Indicating Element Concentration Signify Significant Differences

Conclusions

According to obtained results there are differences between aquaculture systems and

rivers in the accumulation of zn, cu , and cd. Meanwhile, hg recorded its highest values in the cage system compared to ponds and rivers in the gills of common carp. Regarding the

accumulation of Zn and Cu, a significant difference was observed in samples taken from earthen ponds compared to cages and rivers. This is probably due to the long period during which the fish interact with the same water in the ponds.

From the above, it can be concluded that aquatic organisms can be used as indicators of water quality and as an important measure for implementing sustainable development on these water bodies. They serve as indicators of the extent to which water contains waste and heavy elements, striving to achieve the best treatments to maintain them and preserve human health.

References

- Abbas, L. M., Wahab, N. K., Salman, N. A., & Abu-Elheni, K. J. (2016). Effect of stocking density and partitioning of rearing period on growth, feed utilization and production of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) raised in floating cages. *American Journal of Experimental Agriculture*, 11(4), 1.
- African Journal of Advanced Pure and Applied Sciences. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.aasjournals.com/index.php/ajapas/index>
- Al-Khafaji, B. Y., & Lazim, I. I. (2013). Concentration of some trace elements in liver and muscle of two species of fish in Euphrates River near the center of Al-Nassiriya city-south Iraq. *University of Thi-Qar Journal of Science*, 3(4).
- Al-Khafaji, B. Y., & Lazim, I. I. (2013). Concentration of some trace elements in liver and muscle of two species of fish in Euphrates River near the center of Al-Nassiriya city-south Iraq. *University of Thi-Qar Journal of Science*, 3(4), 24–33.
- APHA. (2003). *Standard methods for the examination of water and wastewater* (20th ed.). Washington, DC: American Public Health Association.
- Balq, O., Alarefee, H., & Zahmoul, T. (2023). Determination of cadmium concentration in the tissues and organs of three fish species collected from Sabratha Fishing Port, Libya. *African Journal of Advanced Pure and Applied Sciences*, 2(2), 1–12.
- Blackmore, G. (2000). Field evidence of metal transfer from invertebrate prey to an intertidal predator, *Thais clavigera* (Gastropoda: Muricidae). *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 51(2), 127–139. <https://doi.org/10.1006/ecss.2000.0643>
- Fahad, K. (2014). Ecology study compared to some probable pollutants to Euphrates River, M'assab-Alaam River and Garraf River in Al-Nasryia city – Iraq. *AL-Muthanna Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 2(1), 61–65.
- FAO. (2015). Cultured aquatic species information programme: *Ctenopharyngodon idellus*. *FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Department*. Retrieved from [http://www.fao.org/fishery/culturedspecies/Ctenopharyngodon idellus/en](http://www.fao.org/fishery/culturedspecies/Ctenopharyngodon%20idellus/en)
- Farhood, A. T. (2015). Bioaccumulation of some trace elements in muscles of two species of fishes in Euphrates River near the center of Suq Al-Shouyukh city-south Iraq. *University of Thi-Qar Journal of Science*, 5(2), 4–10.
- Hassan, F. M., Saleh, M. M., & Salman, J. M. (2010). A study of physicochemical parameters and nine heavy metals in the Euphrates River, Iraq. *Journal of Chemistry*, 7(3), 685–692.
- IBM Corp. (2020). *IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows* (Version 26.0) [Software]. Armonk, NY: IBM Corp.
- Ibrahim, A., AL-Smuay, K., AL-Tarhony, A., & AL-Rakhes, R. (2020). Study of accumulation of some heavy elements in the waving of four types of fish collected from the beaches of Tripoli and Misrata. *Journal of Humanitarian and Applied Sciences*, 5(10), 131–144. Retrieved from <https://khsj.elmergib.edu.ly/index.php/jhas/article/view/301>
- Jasim, R. M., & Fahad, K. K. (2023). Study of the concentration level of heavy metals in water and some tissues of common carp, *Cyprinus carpio* L., which is cultured in cages in the Euphrates River. *University of Thi-Qar Journal of Agricultural Research*, 12(2), 247–256. <https://doi.org/10.54174/utjagr.v12i2.266>
- Joudah, S. K., & Kadhim Fahad, K. (2023, December). Bioaccumulation of some heavy metals (cadmium, copper, and zinc) in three

tissues of the common carp *Cyprinus carpio* L. collected from a mud culture. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 1262, No. 7, p. 072068). IOP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1262/7/072068>

Kassam, L., Subasinghe, R., & Phillips, M. (2011). Aquaculture farmer organizations and cluster management: Concepts and experiences. Retrieved from <https://openknowledge.fao.org/handle/10986/27372>

Khanipour, A. A., Ahmadi, M., & Seifzadeh, M. (2018). Study on bioaccumulation of heavy metals (cadmium, nickel, zinc, and lead) in the muscle of wels catfish (*Silurus glanis*) in the Anzali Wetland. *Iranian Journal of Fisheries Sciences*, 17(3), 545–555. <https://doi.org/10.22092/ijfs.2018.118782>

Nijdam, D., Rood, T., & Westhoek, H. (2012). The price of protein: Review of land use and carbon footprints from life cycle assessments of animal food products and their substitutes. *Food Policy*, 37(6), 760–770.

Olaifa, F. E., Olaifa, A. K., & Onwude, T. E. (2004). Lethal and sub-lethal effects of copper to the African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) juveniles. *African Journal of Biomedical Research*, 7(2), 65–70. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ajbr.v7i2.54071>

Othman, C. O., Khidhir, Z. K., & Arif, E. D. (2023). Bioaccumulation of some heavy metals in the muscle of *Cyprinus carpio* from three locations in Dukan Lake. *Tikrit Journal for Agricultural Sciences*, 23(4), 95–106. <https://doi.org/10.25130/tjas.23.4.9>

Rasheed, R. (2012). Assessment of some heavy metals in muscle tissue of *Silurus triostegus* from Derbendikhan reservoir, Kurdistan Region–Iraq. *Rafidain Journal of Science*, 23(1), 11–18.